
FROM THE HISTORY OF REPRESSIONS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN IN THE 1930S

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8425781>

By **A. Ermanov**

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract

In this article, the author, A. Ermanov, explores the history of repressions that took place in Karakalpakstan in the 1930s. He focuses on the political terror that permeated society at that time and its impact on the lives of local residents. Through the analysis of archival sources and documents from the Central State Archive of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the author reveals the scale of the repressions, their victims, and the methods employed. The article also mentions the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute and its role in those events. The study offers a deep analysis of the historical period, providing a better understanding of the tragic consequences of the repressions in Karakalpakstan in the 1930s and their influence on society and education in the region.

In Uzbekistan during the period of 1937-1953, approximately 100,000 people fell victim to repression. Just in 1937-1939, for "counterrevolutionary activities" in Karakalpakstan, 3,139 individuals were convicted, out of whom 1,431 were repressed, including 459 leading officials [1, 33].

In 1937, the leaders of Karakalpakstan, I.S. Aliyev, D. Rizaev, K. Baltaev, and G.F. Kvachev, were expelled from the party ranks and subjected to repression. Islam Sadykovich Aliyev served as the First Secretary of the Karakalpak Regional Committee of the CPSU (B) from April 1933 to May 25, 1937. On October 4, 1938, during an extramural session of the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court of the former USSR, he was accused under Articles 58, 63, 64, 67 of the Criminal Code of the Uzbek SSR and sentenced to the highest measure of punishment.

Davlet Rizaev was the leader of the Karakalpak Regional Party Organization from May 25 to July 28, 1937. On August 3, 1937, he was accused of nationalism and arrested. Unable to withstand the conditions of imprisonment and interrogations, he attempted to take his own life on September 30 and died at the age of 35.

Karim Baltaev headed the Karakalpak Regional Party Organization from September 2 to October 11, 1937. He was arrested by the NKVD of the Kazakh SSR

as an "enemy of the people," and the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court of the former USSR sentenced him under Articles 58, 63, 64, 67 of the Criminal Code of the Uzbek SSR to the highest measure of punishment.

Georgy Fedorovich Kvachev was appointed Deputy Commissioner of Agriculture of the Kazakh SSR in 1937. From June to September 5, 1937, he temporarily performed the duties of the First Secretary of the Karakalpak Regional Party Organization. On September 13, 1937, the party's regional committee accused G.F. Kvachev of supporting bourgeois nationalists and obstructing the party purge in connection with the "enemy of the people" D. Manzhara. V.G. Kvachev, who was arrested on September 13, 1937, was executed a year later on October 13, 1938, according to Articles 58, 63, 64, 67 of the Criminal Code of the Uzbek SSR.

The same fate befell the secretaries of the Karakalpak Regional Party Committee, Kamildzhan Alimov and Kazakhbay Allabergenov. K. Alimov served as the second secretary of the Karakalpak Regional Party Committee from 1934 to 1937. On October 12, 1937, he was arrested on charges of "bourgeois nationalism" and creative ties to the "counter-revolutionary group" led by Akmal Ikramov. On October 13, 1938, the military collegium of the former USSR Supreme Court sentenced him to the highest measure of punishment under Articles 58, 63, 64, and 67.

K. Allabergenov headed the Regional Court of Karakalpak Autonomous Oblast in 1926-1927. He led the organizational department of the Karakalpak Regional Party Committee from 1927 to 1932. From 1932 to 1934, he served as the third secretary of the Karakalpak Regional Party Committee. He was first repressed in 1935 and rehabilitated a year later. After that, he worked as the head of the personnel department of the People's Commissariat of the Kazakh Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic (KKASSR). In July 1937, the NKVD of KKASSR arrested K. Allabergenov for his participation in the "Group of Four." On October 13, 1938, the military collegium of the former USSR Supreme Court sentenced him to the highest measure of punishment under Articles 58, 63, 64, and 67.

The former chairman of the Central Executive Committee (CEC) of the Karakalpak Autonomous Oblast and later the autonomous republic, Koptleu Nurmammedov, also did not escape repression. The fate of one of the prominent statesmen of Karakalpakstan, Kasym Avezov, tragically unfolded. K. Nurmammedov worked as the deputy prosecutor of the Karakalpak Autonomous Oblast from March to June 1928. From 1929 to 1933, he headed the Executive Committee of the Karakalpak Autonomous Oblast, and later the CEC of the Karakalpak Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic (ASSR). From 1934 to 1937,

he held various positions in Moscow, Uzbekistan, and Kazakhstan. On October 17, 1937, he was arrested by Lieutenant V. Shtein of the NKVD of KKASSR, who prepared information about K. Nurmammedov's involvement in counter-revolutionary groups. In 1938, the 35-year-old Koptleu Nurmammedov was sentenced to the highest measure of punishment.

In November 1924 to June 1925, Kasym Avezov headed the Department of Public Education of the Executive Committee of the Karakalpak Autonomous Oblast. From 1925 to 1929, Kasym Avezov led the Executive Committee of the Karakalpak Autonomous Oblast and simultaneously served as the Deputy of the Central Executive Committee of the Kazakh ASSR. He worked as the People's Commissar of Agriculture in Kazakhstan. In 1930-1931, he was appointed as the permanent representative of Karakalpakstan to the Council of People's Commissars of the RSFSR (Moscow). From 1932 to 1934, upon returning to his homeland, he worked as the third secretary of the Karakalpak Party Committee, and later as the Chairman of the Council of People's Commissars of the KKASSR. In 1935-1936, he was again appointed as the permanent representative of the Karakalpak ASSR to the Council of People's Commissars of the RSFSR (Moscow). From April 1936 to September 10, 1937, he headed the Department of Arts under the Council of People's Commissars of the KKASSR.

On September 3, 1937, the Party Control Meeting of the Central Committee of the VKP(b) in Karakalpakstan reviewed Kasym Avezov's party case, accusing him of deceit during his admission to the party, organizing the "Group of Four," and abandoning his national views. On September 30, the regional party organization expelled him from the party and Soviet bodies. On October 13, 1938, the Military Collegium of the former USSR Supreme Court sentenced him to the highest measure of punishment based on Articles 58, 63, 64, and 67.

Based on artificially compromising materials from the NKVD of the KKASSR (with Lieutenant V. Shtein as the immediate organizer and collector of these materials), hundreds of party and state officials were declared "enemies of the people" and executed, including Zhumabay Kurbanov, Kalimulla Bajanov, Yakshimurat Dzhanaliev, Utenyaz Bekimbetov, Abu Kudabaev, Aizhan Bekmuratova, Seyt Toreev, Turdymurat Nizamatinov, Allanazar Pirnazarov, Ismetulla Bekbauliev, Sabyr Klychev, and Allaniyaz Aiteshov. On October 13, 1938, the Military Collegium of the former USSR Supreme Court sentenced 22 individuals to the highest measure of punishment, execution.

The first secretaries of the party district committees were arrested for "counter-revolutionary activities" - Mahmudin Imamnazarov, V.P. Valiullin, Ibaydulla

Abdrakhmanov, Mambet Vabgachev, Ibragim Mambetaliyev, Atabaev, Turkmenbai Taumanov, and Pahratdin Usmanov. The Chairmen of the District Executive Committees who were repressed include Seyfutdin Davletmuratov, Baltabai Bekmurzaev, Bazar Yusupov, Orazymbet Dilmanov, and Sultan Karabaev.

Member of the All-Union Central Executive Committee of the USSR, Chairman of the Kirov collective farm in the Chimbay district, Esen Abiev, Secretary of the Presidium of the Supreme Council of the KKASSR, Fahrattin Sunchaliev, members of the Supreme Court of the republic, S.N. Seifi, K. Irmanov, prosecutors of the Kegayly district, Sultan Kozybaev, and Khodzhayly district, Baymukhan Kuramysov, along with many other illustrious sons of the people, fell victim to the repressive machine.

In total, approximately 9,000 people were arrested from 1934 to 1939, including 495 leading workers. By May 1938, 2,538 people had been convicted. Nearly all the leading workers of Karakalpakstan, including 10 secretaries and heads of departments of the regional party organization, 26 secretaries of district party committees, 22 people's commissars of the republic, 12 heads of district executive committees, 36 law enforcement officials, 30 collective farm and village council chairpersons, and several hundred representatives of the intelligentsia and clergy, were repressed.

Alongside political repression, repression in the field of the national economy was also gaining momentum. In the Taktakupyr district at the end of 1937, 27 people were expelled from collective farms for their connection to "enemies of the people" and their family's past affiliation with the clergy.

According to the agricultural regulations, collective farm members had the right to individually use between 0.3 and 0.4 hectares of household land. However, in most collective farms in the northern regions of Karakalpakstan, individual plots of collective farm members ranged from 0.3 to 3 hectares. The majority of their labor was spent on their individual fields, neglecting the cultivation of collective farm fields.

The chairman of the "Madaniyat" collective farm in the Kungrad district, Bekmurza Tureev, had 3 hectares of personal cultivation on collective farm land, including crops such as wheat, barley, millet, and vegetables. He worked this land using the collective farm's oxen and agricultural equipment. The chairman of the "Karakalpakstan" collective farm, Utenyaz Tursynbekov, had his own crops: vegetables - 0.5 hectares, wheat - 1 hectare, barley - 0.3 hectares, millet - 1.2 hectares, carrots - 0.3 hectares, totaling 3.3 hectares. His relative, who lived with him, worked this land using the collective farm's labor force and equipment. The

NKVD administration of Uzbekistan in Karakalpakstan opened a case against them.

The chairman of the village council No. 2 in the Khodzhayli district, Sangibay Tynyshykov, together with Beket Permenov, planted crops on the land of the "Socialism" collective farm: wheat - 1.5 hectares, potatoes - 0.5 hectares, sesame - 0.5 hectares, barley - 0.5 hectares, totaling 3 hectares, which were cultivated by the collective farm's labor force. The chairman of the Urzhay village council in the Chimbay district, B. Sultanov, had a cultivation of wheat on 0.75 hectares in the "Bakhytly" collective farm, which was cultivated by the collective farm members without payment for their labor. The chairman of this collective farm, Zh. Erimbetov, had a cultivation of wheat - 1.2 hectares and onions - 1.2 hectares.

A significant group of "wandering collective farmers" emerged - in 1939, out of 135,000 able-bodied collective farmers, 7,722 people did not participate in collective farm production, and in 1940, 988 people were not involved in collective farm production.

Inspections and measurements showed that out of 45,710 collective farms in Karakalpakstan, 8,118 had plots exceeding the established norm by more than a tenth of a hectare, and 611 farms had no household plots at all. A total of 7,608 hectares of land were confiscated and distributed to farms that had no household plots.

The editor of the newspaper "Zhas Leninshi," Izbasar Fazilov, was charged with the following offenses: since 1935, he had been a member of a nationalist counter-revolutionary organization and deliberately did not publish the youth newspaper on time. Starting in 1937, the newspaper was published three times a month, resulting in a loss of half of its subscribers. He praised members of the nationalist counter-revolutionary organization and published anti-Soviet poems by N. Zhapakov and S. Mazhitov in the newspaper.

On November 10, 1938, in the city of Almaty, an off-site session of the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court of the former USSR took place. The case of I. Fazilov was considered by judges Alexeev (chairman), Zaitsev, and Boldyrev (members). The session lasted for 20 minutes, and the court sentenced I. Fazilov to 10 years of imprisonment. He was sent to Zlatoust Prison in the Chelyabinsk Oblast, and later to a labor correctional camp in the Magadan Oblast of the Russian Federation.

I. Fazilov's spouse filed an appeal for a review of the case. On March 17, 1941, Prosecutor Savosin of the 2nd Rank of the Military Prosecutor's Office of the Turkestan District rejected this appeal. On October 18, 1950, I. Fazilov returned

from exile to the Taktakupyr District. However, two months later, on December 20, 1950, he was arrested again. The arrest was sanctioned by the acting prosecutor of the Karakalpak Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic (KKASSR), Akchurin.

Senior Agent of the Fifth Division of the State Security Ministry (MGB) of the KKASSR, Senior Lieutenant Ergaliyev, having reviewed the materials on Izbasar Fazilov, born in 1908 in the Bozatau region of the Taktakupyr District of the KKASSR, a Karakalpak citizen of the USSR, literate, sentenced by the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court of the USSR on November 10, 1938, under Articles 14-64 and 67 of the Criminal Code of the Uzbek SSR, to 10 years of imprisonment, having served the term in 1948, currently residing in the settlement of Taktakupyr with no specific occupation, found that I. Fazilov was a participant in an anti-Soviet nationalist terrorist organization operating in the KKASSR. Under the instructions of the said anti-Soviet nationalist terrorist organization, Fazilov, working as the editor of the republican newspaper "Zhas Leninshi" and a member of the board of the Union of Writers of the KKASSR, conducted subversive work on the ideological front, aimed at spreading and producing counter-revolutionary nationalist literature.

Based on the articles 49, paragraph "v," and 51 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Uzbek SSR, it was decided to arrest and search I. Fazilov. The Chief of the 5th Division of the State Security Ministry (MGB) of the KKASSR, Major Vinogradov, agreed with the decision. From March 3, 1951, to July 11, 1957, while in exile, I. Fazilov worked in a geological exploration expedition in the Krasnoyarsk Krai.

On July 13, 1957, the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court of the former USSR overturned the verdict and discontinued the case against him due to the absence of elements of the crime.

"The end of the 1930s, the Second World War, the restoration of the national economy. It was during these years that our elders led the republic [7]. As known, these were years of deprivation and hardships when the living conditions of people sharply deteriorated, and state support was significantly reduced. The land was plowed with bulls or donkeys, or even by hand, and watered with a bucket. In these difficult years of trials, the elders faithfully served for the benefit of the motherland, the prosperity, and further development of the republic, feeding and caring for the unity of the people" [8,15].

All of them, to some extent, experienced the allure of intrigues cultivated by the regime, the audacious interference of the authorities. During the totalitarian regime, history was deprived of its heroes, martyrs, and statesmen. They sought to distort it beyond recognition or completely remove it from the real world-historical

process. The erasure of inconvenient figures from books and textbooks became the norm.

The repressive machine of the totalitarian system also attempted to swallow another statesman of Karakalpakstan, Pirzhan Seitov. On September 26, 1937, Assistant to the Operative Authorized of the Khodjeyli District Division of the NKVD, Abdullin, interrogated Pirnazar Turumbetov, the secretary of the district Komsomol committee, who stated that Pirzhan Seitov had close ties with the spiritual leader Amani Azakhun. The Chief of the Khodjeyli District Division of the NKVD, Junior Lieutenant of State Security Zagretdinov, pointed out to P. Seitov that during his leadership of the district executive committee in the Khodjeyli District, he reinstated Kuben Temirov into the party [9].

In a letter from the Prosecutor of the Karakalpak Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic (ASSR) to the Secretary of the Karakalpak Regional Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU), K. Khalikeev, dated May 4, 1939, it was stated that NKVD officer Vrzhezhevsky was actively preparing compromising materials with the help of prisoners Pankratov and Sokolov in order to accuse P. Seitov of connections with a Trotskyist group [10]. At the same time, an instructor from the Organizational and Instructional Department of the Karakalpak Regional Committee of the CPSU, Bataev, prepared a "Conclusion on the Case of Pirzhan Seitov," where he accused him of failing to expose the kulak Tlegenov, as they were fellow villagers. This was mentioned in the article "Vigilance of Khodjeyli Leaders" in the newspaper "Sovetskaya Karakalpakia" on October 9, 1938. It was also claimed that as the People's Commissar of Agriculture, P. Seitov was inactive in implementing measures to eliminate the consequences of harmful activities within the system of the People's Commissariat of Agriculture of the Karakalpak ASSR (based on the speeches of deputy of the Supreme Council of the Karakalpak ASSR Ahmadiev, reports from Daryan and Sobolev). It was alleged that P. Seitov, at the direction of Kulenov, actively participated in organizing nationalist meetings in Tashkent during the seventh congress of the CPSU (based on statements from Tsuprikov and Chukanov). P. Seitov was accused of allocating unsuitable land with high groundwater levels (0.4 meters) for economic construction to Korean settlers (based on a survey report and a memorandum from Anisiforov). P. Seitov was also accused of having connections with "enemies of the people" I. Fazilov, Kuchkarov, A. Musayev, and K. Allabergenov (based on an article in the newspaper "Kyzyl Karakalpakstan" dated October 20, 1937) [11].

Pirzhan Seitov denied these accusations in his reports addressed to the Regional Committee of the CPSU and the Central Committee of the CPSU. The

accusations were not substantiated, and the storm of repression passed by. Thus, in the 1930s, there was no "spring breeze" blowing over Karakalpakstan; instead, the clouds of Stalinism grew darker. The destructive process of conforming people's thinking to a predetermined template was underway, and spiritual emptiness was increasing. As a result, the ranks of the national intelligentsia, collective farmers, and workers were thinning out.

LITERATURE AND SOURCES:

1. Babashev, Sh. Political Terror in Karakalpakstan in 1937-1938. Materials of the Scientific Session of the Academic Council dedicated to the results of the 2000 research. Nukus, 2001.
2. Babashev, Sh.B. Victims of Political Repression in Karakalpakstan (1937-1938). Bulletin of the Karakalpak Branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2001, No. 4.
3. State Archive of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (SARK), Fond 1, Opus 4, File 1779, Page 129.
4. SARK, Fond 322, Opus 1, File 130, Pages 27-31.
5. SARK, Fond 1, Opus 33, File 17, Page 17.
6. SARK, Fond 1, Opus 121, File 19, Page 320.
7. Implied individuals: P. Seitov, M. Zhumanazarov, N. Zhapakov.
8. Kamalov, K. In the Service of the People. Historical Essays. Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 1995.
9. SARK, Fond 1, Opus 4, File 1933, Pages 86-93.
10. SARK, Fond 1, Opus 4, File 2248, Page 66.
11. SARK, Fond 1, Opus 12, File 61, Page 76.